

THE INFLUENCE OF ORGANIZATIONAL FACTORS ON JOB SATISFACTION OF HUMAN RESOURCES IN DADI REGIONAL SPECIAL HOSPITAL, SOUTH SULAWESI PROVINCE

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the influence of organizational factors on job satisfaction at the Dadi Regional General Hospital (RSUD) in South Sulawesi Province. The research method employed is quantitative research with a cross-sectional design, involving a sample of 100 respondents selected through probability sampling using a questionnaire as the research instrument. The results indicate that variables such as teamwork, reward & recognition, communication, and working conditions do not significantly influence job satisfaction in the hospital. On the other hand, variables like leadership, empowerment & participation, training & individual development, and working hours significantly affect job satisfaction. Leadership has an influence 3.351 times greater on job satisfaction, empowerment & participation has an influence 2.895 times greater, training & individual development has an influence 3.491 times greater, and working hours has an influence 3.645 times greater on job satisfaction. Positive and supportive leadership styles can enhance employee job satisfaction. Empowered employees tend to take pride in their work and perceive a greater purpose, significantly improving job satisfaction. Properly identifying and meeting training needs can enhance job satisfaction, and attention to employee conditions and patient service needs is crucial in setting working hours. Although teamwork, reward & recognition, communication, and working conditions were found to have no significant influence, they remain important in enhancing employee performance in the hospital.

Keywords: Empowerment & Participation, Working Condition, Communication, Leadership.

INTRODUCTION

Hospitals are institutions constantly demanded to improve the quality of their services. The quality of hospital services is influenced by various factors, and one of them is the role of human resources within the hospital. Various professions working in hospitals contribute to setting the standards and quality of services provided. Human Resources (HR) is considered the most valuable asset for organizations or companies compared to other assets because other assets cannot function effectively without HR intervention. Therefore, maintaining human resources becomes a crucial factor for the efficient and effective operation of activities within an organization to achieve its goals.

Employee satisfaction surveys in hospitals show varied results, but generally fall below the standards set by the hospitals. Factors influencing employee job satisfaction in hospitals include recognition, autonomy, acknowledgment, opportunities for development, working hours, and patient appreciation. Employee job satisfaction in hospitals significantly affects the performance of nurses and other healthcare professionals. Therefore, job satisfaction becomes a crucial factor in improving the quality of hospital services [1]; [2].

The positive impact of job satisfaction in hospitals extends to employee productivity. Employees who are satisfied with their work tend to be more motivated and enthusiastic, leading to increased productivity. Conversely, dissatisfied employees are less motivated and less enthusiastic, resulting in decreased productivity. Moreover, good job satisfaction can enhance the quality of patient care and patient satisfaction, reducing negative behaviors such as deficiencies, grievances, and high stress levels [3].

Good job satisfaction can help medical staff boost confidence and professionalism, promote genuine behavior in fulfilling their duties, improve relationships with colleagues, and effectively reduce job stress, thereby positively impacting job performance [4].

Dadi Regional Special Hospital in South Sulawesi Province is one of the organizations owned by the South Sulawesi Provincial Government, classified as a Class A Special Hospital providing comprehensive health services. It specializes in mental health services and also offers general health services such as neurology, surgery, internal medicine, cardiology, and other physical diseases. The evaluation conducted by the Governor's Team for the Acceleration of Development in South Sulawesi (TGUPP-Sulsel) at Dadi Regional Special Hospital in South Sulawesi Province in 2022 indicated that the employee satisfaction level was subpar, with an achievement of 70%, not meeting the standard of 76.61% - 88.30% (good).

Furthermore, the Employee Satisfaction Survey results in 2022 at Dadi Regional Special Hospital in South Sulawesi Province, conducted by the Quality Committee Team of the hospital, revealed a satisfaction level of 67% in the first semester, falling below the standard of 76.61% - 88.30% according to Regulation of the Minister of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform (Permenpan-RB) No. 14 of 2017. The evaluation criteria for the four variables include Workspace Assessment with an achievement of 72%, Facility Assessment with an achievement of 63%, Personnel Administration Services with an achievement of 71%, and Financial Services with an achievement of 64%.

Considering the unsatisfactory achievement levels of employee satisfaction at Dadi Regional Special Hospital in South Sulawesi Province, it can be inferred that financial and non-financial incentive provisions, work motivation, and interpersonal relationships among employees may influence HR job satisfaction at the hospital. Given this context, the researcher is interested in investigating factors contributing to the low achievement of human resources satisfaction at Dadi Regional Special Hospital in South Sulawesi Province.

Hypotheses

H1 = There is an influence of Teamwork on job satisfaction

Teamwork, according to Lawasi and Triatmanto, is the most effective way to unite all employees in performing their tasks to achieve the company's goals with better results. As quoted by Arifin (2020), research indicates that teamwork has a direct and significant influence on employee performance and a positive and significant indirect impact on performance through job satisfaction [5].

H2 = There is an influence of Leadership on job satisfaction

In a study by Munthe et al 2022 on the influence of leadership and organizational culture on employee job satisfaction in the military hospital of Pematangsiantar, the results showed that leadership and organizational culture significantly affect employee job satisfaction.

H3 = There is an influence of Reward & Participation on job satisfaction

Reward and recognition are efforts that a company can make to manage employees and create professional employees according to the demands of their respective positions. Fitria et al 2017 analyzed the influence of reward, incentives, task distribution, and career development on job satisfaction of nurses at Prof. Dr. R. Soeharso Orthopedic Hospital in Surakarta [6]. The results showed that reward, incentives, task distribution, and career development positively and significantly influence job satisfaction.

H4 = There is an influence of Empowerment & Participation on job satisfaction

Samosir et al 2022 determined the cause-and-effect relationship between employee involvement and organizational support on job satisfaction and employee performance, both directly and indirectly [7]. The research found that employee involvement significantly influences job satisfaction and employee performance, while organizational support has a significant positive impact on job satisfaction but no effect on employee performance. Job satisfaction was identified as mediating the relationship between employee involvement and employee performance.

H5 = There is an influence of Training & Individual Development on job satisfaction

Career development, according to Yusuf, is the condition that shows the creation of an individual's status within the company in the predetermined career ladder, related to knowledge, skills, and other abilities. Companies that pay attention to their employees provide continuous development for knowledge, skills, and other abilities. Therefore, career development is done to change conditions and improve job satisfaction, [8].

H6 = There is an influence of Working Hours on job satisfaction

Research by Barili et al 2022 found that long working hours can lead to fatigue, tiredness, and low motivation among healthcare workers, negatively impacting job satisfaction and patient care [9].

Adequate staffing, a pleasant working environment, opportunities for personal and professional growth, reasonable workloads, supervision, recognition, positive relationships with colleagues, job autonomy, job security, career advancement, and contingency rewards are factors influencing company performance and can positively affect job satisfaction among healthcare workers [10].

H7 = There is an influence of Communication on job satisfaction

Hasna et al 2022 define communication as the relationship between the communicator and the communicant that is suitable for a specific message. Proper message delivery is the basis for decision-making [11].

A study by Maulina 2017 tested the influence of communication, self-esteem, and self-efficacy on job satisfaction and performance of nurses at Tengku Fakinah Hospital in Banda Aceh. The results showed no significant influence between communication variables and job satisfaction and nurse performance [12].

H8 = There is an influence of Working Condition on job satisfaction

Employees will always pay attention to the working environment to feel comfortable. Employees dislike unpleasant and unsafe work facilities. Employees desire a work environment that resembles the atmosphere at home.

A study by Padmavathi 2023 to evaluate the influence of sustainable working environment on employee engagement, job satisfaction, and retention in the e-commerce industry showed that a sustainable working environment positively and significantly influences employee engagement, job satisfaction, and retention. Mediation analysis indicates that employee engagement and job satisfaction fully mediate the relationship between sustainable working environment and employee retention [13].

RESEARCH METHODS

Data Collection, Sampling, and Measurement

The research employed a quantitative approach with a cross-sectional design. The study was conducted at Dadi Regional Special Hospital in South Sulawesi Province from November to December 2023.

The population consisted of human resources with Civil Servant (Aparatur Sipil Negara - ASN) status, both government officials (PNS) and non-government officials (Non-PNS), working at Dadi Regional Special Hospital in South Sulawesi Province in 2023. The total population included 417 PNS and 197 Non-PNS, resulting in a total of 614 human resources.

The sample size for the study was determined using the Slovin formula, resulting in a sample of 100 respondents selected through probability sampling. Data collection was conducted using a validated and reliable questionnaire.

The research instrument, a questionnaire, was adapted from the study conducted by Ahmad et al 2020, recruited from three government hospitals in Kuching, Sarawak, Malaysia, and validated (JS-Q), proving its validity. Additionally, the questionnaire used in the study by Frankly and Innocentius at Gunung Maria Hospital in Tomohon in 2021 was also incorporated [14].

Statistical Analysis

The data analysis process involved the use of multiple logistic regression equations. Both univariate and multivariate analyses were conducted. Univariate analysis involved a descriptive examination of the variables by calculating frequency distribution and proportions to understand the characteristics of the research subjects. Multivariate analysis was employed to analyze the influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable through logistic regression analysis.

RESULTS

Table 1: Respondent Characteristics

Respondent Characteristics	N	%
Gender		
Male	26	26
Female	74	74
Total	100	100
Age (Years)		
21-25	6	6
26-30	13	13
31-35	9	9
36-40	11	11
41-45	12	12
46-50	29	29
51-55	11	11
>55	9	9
Total	100	100
Work Unit		
Midwife	2	2
Doctor	9	9
Non-Healthcare	19	19
Nurse	46	46
Non-Medical Healthcare	24	24
Total	100	100
Length of Service in the Hospital		
< 10 Years	33	33
10-20 Years	27	27
21-30 Years	25	25
31-40 Years	12	12
> 40 Years	3	3
Total	100	100
Employment Status		
Civil Servant (PNS)	77	77
Non-Civil Servant (Non-PNS)	23	23
Total	100	100
Highest Education Attainment		
D3	12	12
D4	4	4
Bachelor's Degree (S1)	62	62
Master's Degree (S2)	9	9
High School Graduate (SM)	6	6
Specialist	7	7
Total	100	100

(Source: Primary Data, 2023)

Table 1 shows that the distribution of respondents based on gender shows that there are more female respondents than male respondents. Regarding age, respondents aged 46-50 years are dominant, with 29 respondents, while those aged 21-25 years are the least, with 6 respondents. Based on the work unit, nurses dominate the respondents (46 respondents), and the least represented group is midwives (2 respondents). In terms of length of service in the hospital, respondents working for < 10 years are dominant, with 33 respondents, while those working for > 40 years are the least, with 3 respondents. Employment status indicates that there are more respondents with Civil Servant (PNS) status (77 respondents) compared to Non-Civil

Servant (Non-PNS) status (23 respondents). The highest education attainment shows that the majority have a Bachelor's Degree (S1) (62 respondents), and the least have a Diploma 4 (D4) (4 respondents).

Tabel 2: Distribusi Persepsi Variabel

Variabel	Low		High	
	n	%	n	%
Leadership	62	62,0	38	38,0
Empowerment & Participation	39	39,0	61	61,0
Training & Individual Development	47	47,0	53	53,0
Working Hours	69	69,0	31	31,0
Teamwork	56	56,0	44	44,0
Reward & Recognition	57	57,0	43	43,0
Working Condition	33	33,0	67	67,0
Communication	42	42,0	58	58,0
Job Satisfaction	42	42,0	58	58,0

(Source: Primary Data, 2023)

Table 2 shows that the respondents stated that they feel satisfied at a rate of 58%. The level of employee job satisfaction in the hospital appears to be lower than the previous assessment in 2022, which was 67%. Thus, employee satisfaction has not met the expected target of 76.61% - 88.30%. Additionally, low perceptions were found among most respondents for variables such as leadership, working hours, teamwork, and reward and recognition. On the other hand, high perceptions were found for variables such as empowerment & participation, training & individual development, working conditions, and communication. This indicates that some respondents have both high and low perceptions for each variable, which are organizational factors affecting the community.

Table 3: Hypothesis Testing Results

Influence Variables	Sig.	Exp(B)	Remarks
Teamwork → Job Satisfaction	0,851	1,099	No significant influence of teamwork on job satisfaction
Leadership → Job Satisfaction	0,029	3,351	Significant influence of leadership on job satisfaction
Reward & Recognition → Job Satisfaction	0,997	1,002	No significant influence of reward & recognition on job satisfaction
Empowerment & Participation → Job Satisfaction	0,047	2,895	Significant influence of empowerment & participation on job satisfaction
Training & Individual Development → Job Satisfaction	0,025	3,491	Significant influence of training & individual development on job satisfaction
Working Hours → Job Satisfaction	0,032	3,645	Significant influence of working hours on job satisfaction
Communication → Job Satisfaction	0,617	0,752	No significant influence of communication on job satisfaction
Working Condition → Job Satisfaction	0,243	0,496	No significant influence of working condition on job satisfaction

Table 3 shows that the based on the table above, the variables that have an influence on job satisfaction are leadership, empowerment & participation, training & individual development, and working hours. Meanwhile, teamwork, reward & recognition, communication, and working conditions do not have a significant influence on job satisfaction. To determine the extent of the influence of each significant variable, it can

be observed from the value of Exp (B) or the exponent value. Based on the Exp (B) values, leadership will have an influence 3.351 times on job satisfaction. Empowerment & participation will have an influence 2.895 times on job satisfaction. Training & individual development will have an influence 3.491 times on job satisfaction. Working hours will have an influence 3.645 times on job satisfaction. Based on the magnitude of the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable, the variable that has the most significant influence on job satisfaction is the working hours variable, with an influence of 3.645 times.

DISCUSSION

Influence of Teamwork on Job Satisfaction

The research results indicate that there is no significant influence between teamwork and job satisfaction. The findings show that nearly half of the respondents have perceptions related to teamwork and job satisfaction that are low. Although the research results indicate that teamwork does not influence job satisfaction, some studies show that teamwork has a significant impact on improving employee performance [15]; [16]. This research is not in line with some studies stating that there is a significant influence between teamwork and job satisfaction resulting in improved employee performance [17]; [18]; [19]. This suggests the possibility of a gap among employees in implementing teamwork, which can decrease employee job satisfaction at RSKD Dadi in South Sulawesi Province.

Fundamentally, there is good cooperation among colleagues in carrying out service tasks in the hospital. Although there are some individuals who may not collaborate well in a team because they feel more capable of handling tasks independently. However, teamwork is crucial, especially when acting as a mediator and facing organizational challenges. The comparison between workload, the number of employees, and each employee's role significantly influences employees' perceptions of job satisfaction [20]. Teamwork can enhance competitiveness within the team, aiding in achieving organizational goals, improving work productivity, and addressing professional and individual differences. Thus, all team members can collaborate and find solutions to achieve common goals.

Influence of Leadership on Job Satisfaction

The study indicates that there is a significant impact of leadership on employee job satisfaction at RSKD Dadi in South Sulawesi Province, namely by a factor of 3.351 times, meaning that an improvement in leadership will enhance patient satisfaction. This suggests that the hypothesis is accepted. Findings reveal a low perception of leadership at RSKD Dadi in South Sulawesi Province. Hospital managers should understand the impact of various leadership styles on job satisfaction and employee commitment levels. This research is supported by a study conducted by Specchia et al 2021, demonstrating a significant influence between leadership styles and employee job satisfaction [21]. Transformational leadership has proven to affect motivation and employee satisfaction in hospitals, particularly contributing to higher job satisfaction among nurses and other healthcare professionals [22]; [21]. Leadership communication, particularly trust-building communication, positive communication tone, and transparent information behavior, have been identified to have a significant positive impact on job satisfaction among doctors and other hospital staff [23].

Understanding influences such as leadership styles, communication, and trust-building behaviors of hospital leaders is crucial for hospital management to create a work environment that enhances job satisfaction. This ultimately leads to higher individual job performance levels and better patient care. Strong leadership is associated with higher job satisfaction among healthcare professionals, ultimately impacting the quality of patient care. Effective leadership is crucial to drive quality improvement, motivate staff, and create a positive and ethical work environment. While the research results indicate that employee recognition and acknowledgment do not influence patient satisfaction, both are essential for employees to enhance their motivation and performance in providing hospital services.

Influence of Reward & Recognition on Job Satisfaction

The research indicates that there is no influence of reward & recognition on employee job satisfaction at UPT RSKD Dadi in South Sulawesi Province. Findings reveal a low perception of reward and recognition among employees at UPT RSKD Dadi in South Sulawesi Province. Hospital managers should understand the importance of reward & recognition on job satisfaction and employee commitment levels. A significant portion, namely 57%, has a low perception of receiving rewards and recognition in the hospital.

The belief that employees receive acknowledgment or recognition from hospital managers for their work is a reasonable expectation. Rewards create a positive work environment, motivating employees to work harder and aiding in job retention. Therefore, the reward system should be properly structured to attract and retain qualified employees, motivating them to deliver better job performance.

Measuring the value of a reward & recognition program is an exercise to determine performance indicators that demonstrate improved outcomes compared to before the program was implemented, such as retention, employee satisfaction, patient satisfaction, productivity, and employee engagement. Additionally, healthcare service managers should encourage a balance between effort and reward, provide opportunities for career development and training, and help employees feel valued and appreciated [24].

Influence of Reward & Recognition on Job Satisfaction

The research indicates that there is no influence of reward & recognition on employee job satisfaction at RSKD Dadi in South Sulawesi Province. Findings reveal a low perception of reward and recognition among employees at RSKD Dadi in South Sulawesi Province. Hospital managers should understand the importance of reward & recognition on job satisfaction and employee commitment levels. A significant portion, namely 57%, has a low perception of receiving rewards and recognition in the hospital.

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opportunities for career development and training, and help employees feel valued and appreciated [24].

Influence of Empowerment & Participation on Job Satisfaction

The research results indicate that Empowerment & Participation will have an impact 2,895 times on job satisfaction. This shows that the hypothesis is accepted. The study reveals that respondents have a positive perception of Empowerment & Participation at UPT RS Dadi Susel. Consequently, the respondents have a high level of satisfaction with the empowerment and participation provided by the hospital. Empowerment and participation have a significant influence on job satisfaction, especially in hospitals and healthcare services. Empowered employees tend to take pride in their work and feel a greater sense of purpose, significantly enhancing job satisfaction. When employees are empowered to make decisions and contribute ideas, they are more motivated to perform at their best, resulting in greater job satisfaction. This research aligns with a study conducted by Choi et al 2016, which states that empowerment has a positive and significant impact on job satisfaction [25].

Research has shown that when employees feel empowered in the workplace, it is associated with stronger job performance, job satisfaction, and commitment to the organization. One form of empowerment implemented in hospitals is offering training courses for managers and employees to empower them to make informed decisions and contribute to the organization's success. It is essential for hospital managers to ensure that all employees have the opportunity to be empowered and engaged in achieving organizational goals.

Influence of Training & Individual Development on Job Satisfaction

The research indicates that there is an impact of individual training and development on job satisfaction, approximately 3,491 times concerning job satisfaction. Respondents' perceptions of employee satisfaction signify that the hypothesis is accepted. Individual training and development have a positive impact on job satisfaction in the hospital environment. A study conducted on paramedic staff in the public hospital sector found that training and development practices positively affect job satisfaction [26]. Additionally, this research is supported by Pomaranik & Magdalena's study 2023, conducted on medical professionals in healthcare entities in Poland, revealing a significant relationship between talent development, including training and development programs, and job satisfaction [27].

According to this research, employees feel valued when organizations pay attention to them and provide opportunities for professional development and training. If an organization has a fair and acceptable assessment system, it can create a pleasant work environment, motivating employees to achieve organizational goals. Furthermore, other researchers indicate that motivation, training, and remuneration-based support in professional development are considered crucial issues for the satisfaction of healthcare service personnel [28]. A study conducted in India found that all talent management practices in healthcare organizations can enhance job satisfaction among nurses and organizational commitment [29].

Influence of Working Hours on Job Satisfaction

The research findings indicate a significant influence of working hours on job satisfaction at RSUD Dadi Susel. This suggests that the hypothesis is accepted. The results highlight the low perception of respondents regarding working hours in the

hospital, indicating employee dissatisfaction with working hours considered less flexible for staff. A study by Pratama & Veronika 2022, demonstrated that the flexibility of working hours has a positive impact on work-life balance, job satisfaction, and employee loyalty in hospitals. The results of this research provide an overview that the flexibility of working hours could potentially have a positive effect on the job satisfaction of hospital employees. The arrangement of working hours also has a significant impact on patient satisfaction, where working hours are often associated with the health of employees, particularly related to insomnia, fatigue, and exhaustion, generally linked to a decrease in patient safety [30].

Hospitals determine the working hours of their staff based on various factors and methods. The number of hours required for each patient often determines the number of nurses needed in the field, especially in units such as intensive care units. Additionally, the level of care required by patients also affects the number of staff needed, with more severely ill patients requiring longer hours of care. The determination of working hours is also influenced by the need to ensure that the facility has adequate staff at all times, given the continuous and frequent turnover of patients whose needs are constantly changing. Overall, determining the working hours of hospital staff is a complex process that considers patient needs, staff requirements, and regulatory considerations [31].

Influence of Communication on Job Satisfaction

The research indicates that there is no significant influence of communication on employee job satisfaction at RSKD Dadi Province of South Sulawesi. The findings reveal that employees have a high perception of communication among colleagues and between superiors at RSKD Dadi Province of South Sulawesi. The majority of respondents perceive communication positively, both from superiors to subordinates and among colleagues, at a rate of 58%. Although this value does not yield significant results, employees feel that superiors can communicate their expectations clearly regarding job-related tasks. However, it is noteworthy that the management may not provide adequate explanations behind decisions related to the hospital's key issues. Consequently, employees feel that they lack information about matters that could impact their work.

This research is supported by Heuss & Datta 2023, who found that communication has a weak influence on well-being and job satisfaction. The study examined the quality of information and information behavior's impact on job satisfaction, where the quality of information and information behavior showed a significant correlation with job satisfaction, while the tone of interaction indicated a weaker effect on job satisfaction [23]. Researchers observe that communication indeed plays a crucial role in job satisfaction in hospitals; Vermeir et al 2017 demonstrated that communication affects job satisfaction and turnover among nurses and doctors [32]. Effective communication is vital for efficient team performance, patient care, and overall organizational success [33].

Influence of Work Condition on Job Satisfaction

The research indicates that there is no significant influence of work conditions on employee job satisfaction at RSKD Dadi Province of South Sulawesi. The findings reveal that employees have a high perception of work conditions at RSKD Dadi Province of South Sulawesi, amounting to 67%. Most employees feel that the expected workload is reasonable and aligns with their working conditions. However,

it's worth noting that employees sometimes lack the tools and resources needed to perform their jobs correctly.

This study is supported by Yusnita's 2019, research, which found that work conditions have a low influence on employee job satisfaction, specifically a mere 0.063 in enhancing job satisfaction. Researchers observe that what affects employee job satisfaction in hospitals is the work environment rather than the specific work conditions [34]. The work conditions for hospital employees have been provided according to each employee's situation. The work environment is described as the physical and emotional aspects in the workplace that foster commitment, productivity, and employee satisfaction. A conducive work environment plays a crucial role in stimulating employee job satisfaction, especially in the healthcare industry, which often experiences strikes due to poor working conditions. Physical and emotional aspects, such as determining working conditions, employee rights, employee voices, safe working conditions, cooperative team members, and friendly supervisors, contribute to a positive work environment [35]. Happiness in what one does at the workplace is fundamental to an individual's lifestyle. The same holds true for every hospital employee because their satisfaction positively impacts patient safety, productive work behavior, quality of care and attention, turnover, dedication, job engagement, and their profession [36].

CONCLUSION

Our research demonstrates that the variables of leadership, empowerment & participation, training & individual development, and working hours significantly influence patient satisfaction in hospitals. Positive leadership styles are crucial in creating a positive work environment that retains empowered and motivated workforce. Positive and supportive leadership styles can enhance employee job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and intent to stay while reducing emotional exhaustion. These findings suggest that policy interventions should include leadership and empowerment to enhance job satisfaction among hospital employees.

Training and development have a substantial impact on job satisfaction. If training needs are identified and met adequately and regularly, employees will learn new things to develop their skills, ultimately enhancing their job satisfaction. Training and development programs improve job security, boost trust levels leading to improved teamwork. Well-trained employees can obtain better salaries, motivating them to deliver better performance. Thus, well-planned and designed training programs will provide satisfaction and motivation for the workforce, necessary for effective and efficient hospital practices.

Our findings also examine how working hours influence employee job satisfaction. Working hour arrangements significantly impact patient satisfaction, often linked to employee health, particularly regarding insomnia and fatigue, generally associated with reduced patient safety. Therefore, working hour arrangements need to consider employee conditions and patient service needs. Further research is expected to explore more organizational factors influencing job satisfaction, especially in hospitals, giving significant consideration to how job satisfaction also affects patient satisfaction.

Our research also found that variables such as teamwork, reward & recognition, communication, and working conditions do not significantly affect job satisfaction in hospitals. Teamwork revealed good cooperation among fellow employees in

performing service tasks in the hospital. Although some individuals may struggle to collaborate in a team due to feeling more capable of handling tasks individually. Additionally, the belief that employees receive rewards or recognition from hospital managers for their work is considered a normal part of their job, not affecting their job satisfaction. The research found insufficient communication in providing clear explanations regarding key hospital issues. Consequently, employees feel they lack information about factors that could affect their work. The researchers also observe that what affects employee job satisfaction in hospitals is the work environment rather than specific working conditions. Although these variables were found not to have a significant impact, all variables in this study are important for improving employee performance in hospitals. Therefore, it is crucial for all hospital stakeholders, both management and other employees, to pay attention to all these variables for enhancing employee performance in hospitals. Thus, future researchers can investigate the impact of these variables on employee performance in hospitals, whether mediated by job satisfaction or having a direct effect.

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